

The Coupling Constants Series, Spin Symmetries and Free Electrons – 8T

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing a variation of the coupling constants primorial series, and in particular a reposition of the invariant (3) with the net variation N_V , we can then reason free electrons. Such a variation is valid due to the second representation of the coupling constants series, which is the prime critical line.

Introduction

The coupling constants series is describing the process of emission and absorption of bosons by fermions. By using the recent insight of the coupling series and bosons to be net curvature isomorphic to primes or one given by (1) to (1.31). In the 8T thesis we have proved the invariant three to be an electron, causing the net curvature to appear on the matrix tensor, which is the photon, or $N_V = (+5)$.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Shifting to spin representations for the third element in the series, which is electromagnetism:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Replacing the bold element with the inner element of one-half would count as an invariant transformation which preserve the original structure in spin representation:

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\gamma)] + (e) \quad (1.33)$$

Such a variation of the coupling series does not affect the overall magnitude of the element, but using it we can reason for the existence of free charges in nature. Since this are not bound to matter, they do not have to vanish so nature will allow it. In previous paper we showed that if the original structure would be analyzed the electrons will add up to a positive summation of curvature, which must vanish. Nature than will generate an opposite set of spinning charges to ensure it will and that was the reason monopoles can not exist. (1.34) is the positive summation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N e_i \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N (+3)_i > 0 \quad (1.34)$$

Which belongs to larger cluster of arbitrary variations vanishing into matter. Curvature is not allowed:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N e_i \in \sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k ; M > N \quad (1.35)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (1.36)$$

Those two conditions are in contradiction. The left is a positive curvature summation within a cluster of arbitrary variations which curvature must vanish. The solution is to represent an additional cluster of spinning the inverse direction within the cluster of matter to solve the contradiction of (1.37).

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i > 0 \cap \sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (1.37)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^T (-3)_i < 0 \quad (1.38)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^T (-3)_i + \sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i = 0; \quad T = N \quad (1.39)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (1.40)$$

Summing up, when the electron is bounded by the bracket as given by equation (1.32), nature will not allow to exist by itself, however by symmetry of spin leading to equation (1.33), now the electron is free and such a vanishing of the summation is no longer valid. The equation than suggest an elegant and simple explanation to one of the most interesting enigmas of modern physics – the enigma of free electrons and lack of monopoles within matter.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constant Series and Magnetic Monopoles" In: (2021)